

Annex 2: Missionoceanwaters.eu Sitemap

Main Pages	Sub-Pages	Fly-to-Pages	Info-Points	Info-Points - European Projects & Initiatives mentioned in text box	Testimonials & Statements on Fly-to-Pages	Other Info Boxes	Notes
Homepage							
	Protected - Destroyed						Presents Mission Objective 1: Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity
	Pristine - Polluted						Presents Mission Objective 2: Prevent and eliminate pollution
	Prosperous - Exploited						Presents Mission Objective 3: Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular
Lighthouse North & Baltic Sea			Baltic and North Sea Lighthouse				
			Climate and Weather	EU Climate-ADAPT			
			Tourism				
			Early Career Scientists	Atlantic ECOP Programme			
				APECS			
				Global ECOP Programme			
		More about the Mission	Vegetables from the Sea	OLAMUR	Kestutis Sadauskas (COM), n.n. (DK), Andreas Reinhardt (DE), Lars Baumler (DE), Karen Wiltshire (DE), Katja Matthes (DE), n.n. (NO),		
				ULTFARMS			
			Emissions and Pollution				
		Plastic Pirates	More about Plastic Pirates				
			Plastic Pollution in the Sea				
		More about citizen science	Citizen Science	EU4OCEAN			
			Citizen science in action	EU-Citizen.Science Database			
		What tools do I need for citizen science?	Citizen Science	CitieS-Health Toolkit			
				CoastSnap Spain			

				EMB Citizen Science study			
				Ocean Citizen website			
				EU-Citizen.Science database			
			Plastic Pirates	PlasticPirates Go Europe			
			Where does scientific data get published?	EMODNET			
				WISE Marine			
				Copernicus Marine Service			
		Port	Ports of the Future				
			Climate Change Impacts	CLIMAREST			
			Ocean Observation	JERICO-RI			
			Algae – Friend or Foe?	EU Oder Report			
				EU Algae Strategy			
				AlgaeProBANOS			
			Blue Economy	EU Blue Economy Report 2023			
				Interreg-Euro-Med Programme			
			Ports and Shipping	Green shipping projects overview			
Lighthouse Atlantic & Arctic			Mission Statement				
			A Rescue Ring for our Ocean and Waters	EU Mission Ocean and Waters database			
			Ocean				
		Catherine's Mission			Catherine Sheridan (IRL)		
		Lighthouse	Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse				
			Discover Europe's Lighthouses				
		Shore					
		Estuaries	Estuaries	REST-COAST			
				CoastalWiki			
		Ghost Ship	Shipwrecks	North Sea Wrecks			
Lighthouse Mediterranean			Mediterranean Lighthouse	BlueMissionMed	Inès Boujmil (TUN)		
			Programmes for Early-Career Scientists				
				EU Youth4Ocean			

		More about the Mission			John Bell (COM), Isabelle Sousa-Pinto (PT), Luis Vera (PT), Sergio Rossi Heras (IT), Dimitros Alexopolous (GR), Fedra Francocci (IT), Rym Benzina Bourguiba (TUN), Jose Moutinho, Figen Ayan (TUR),		
		Protected Sea	Seagrass	EMODNET Seabed Habitats			
				LIFE-TRANSFER			
			Tourism	EU Blue Economy Report			
				Sustainable tourism projects list			
		Degraded Sea	Ghost Nets	NETTAGPlus			
				SEARCULAR			
			Turbidity	COPERNICUS Lake Water Quality			
			Plastics Pollution in the Sea	REMEDIES			
				SEACLEAR2.0			
				INSPIRE			
				UPSTREAM			
		Protected Coasts	Coastal Protection and Restoration	ERODES			
				MaCoBios: evidence-based guidance for marine policy formulation			
				MACOBIOS			
				FUTUREMARES			
			Islands	SOCLIMPACT			
		Pristine and Polluted Beaches	Plastic Pollution	JRC-University of Cadiz Plastics Tracking Tool			
				MAELSTROM			
Lighthouse Danube & Black Sea			Danube and Black Sea Lighthouse	EcoDALLI			
				DANUBE4All			
				DALIA			
				List to Danube projects			
			Restoring River Ecosystems				
							Menu Pages are structured as traditional webpages

Menu Pages	About						Describes the Mission in basic terms and provides links to further information
	Explore						
	Connect					Mission Ocean and Waters Help Desk	Connect Menu Page Info boxes present further resources available to interested parties to help them connect with the Mission and Mission partners
						The Mission on Social Media	
						Mission Lighthouses	
						Mission Ocean and Waters Digital Academy	
						Citizen science	
						Mission Events	
						Mission Charter	
						Mission Project Database	
	Academy						
	Imprint						